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PROFESSIONAL PRACTICE IN ENGINEERING EDUCATION: LESSONS LEARNED FROM STUDENTS PARTICIPATING IN INTERNSHIPS

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ABSTRACT

This research paper explores the experiences of undergraduate engineering students who completed internships as part of their academic program. Engineering programs are required to fulfil industry needs and prepare students to develop the competencies required in the workforce. We used a qualitative study design to investigate the engineering students' experiences doing internships in the United States. Data were collected using semi-structured interviews and the interview protocol was informed by the boundary-spanning framework. Results report the different aspects of the internship that students found valuable, and the most salient topics were their boundary spanning role, coordination and communication, knowledge and learning, problems and preparation.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

The engineering field has evolved considerably in the last decades. Engineers are required to have the knowledge and competencies to solve contemporary problems and have a positive societal and economic impact. Hence, engineering schools are required to develop engineering graduates that have the competencies that are required by the engineering workforce and in the professional societies and accreditation entities. However, engineering graduates are faced with challenges of entering a completely new environment [1]. Part of the problem is the lack of opportunities in the classroom to replicate industry-like experiences. Nevertheless, research suggests that experiential learning can provide some of those opportunities [2]–[4], more specifically, professional internships provide one of the most significant learning opportunities for students [2], [5]–[8]. Hence, Universities have been promoting internship opportunities for engineering students, some Engineering Schools in some countries even have mandatory internship programs. However, there is not much research conducted on the value that internships bring to engineering students.

The purpose of this paper is to understand engineering students' perceptions of the value of their internship experience. Specifically, we want to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the perceptions engineering students have about their internship experience?

In this paper, we report preliminary results from interviews conducted with engineering students after having an internship experience.

1.2 Theoretical framework

In this study, we used the Boundary Spanning framework [9] that provides a unique lens to understand the realities of engineering work as experienced by practicing engineers. The framework fully unpacks aspects of working with people within an engineering organization: including classification of types of boundaries (cultural, educational, demographics, job role, organizational) and boundary spanning activities (managing information, coordinating, networking, representing and influencing). We selected this framework because we wanted to identify students' different interactions when working in a professional environment and how those interactions influenced their internship experience. In addition, our work is framed by the American Board of Accreditation and Technology (ABET) criteria [10] who developed expected abilities, skills, values, and attitudes that must be demonstrated by engineers at the point of entry to the engineering practice. The integration of the dimensions of the two aforementioned frameworks provided a solid underpinning for the study since we were able not only to understand how well the competencies that are required for engineering students in the U.S. are present when working as a student in a professional experience but also how the different interactions and roles students had shaped the experiential learning opportunity.

2 METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this study is to understand students' experiences doing internships. Since our primary objective is to understand students' experiences qualitative methods that provide rich descriptions are appropriate [11]–[13]. Qualitative research is based on the examination of a phenomenon by using data directly from the participants that experience it [18], based on the examination of the context and complexity of the real-world setting of the phenomenon in order to have an integral understanding of it [14], [15]. We conducted semi-structured interviews with engineering students after participating in an internship experience. Interviews were conducted online and in person and were audio-recorded. The total duration was approximately one hour, and students signed a consent form to participate. The recordings were then transcribed using an online software. To ensure confidentiality, the transcription was cleaned by using pseudonyms and identifiable data was removed. The study secured ethical clearance. Participants were engineering students at a Research University in the United States that had participated in an internship. Table 1 provides more information on the demographics of the participants including the details of the participants' internship roles and company type.

Table 1. Participants' information

#	Engineering program	Gender	Ethnicity	Role	Company Type
P1	Industrial and Systems Engineering	Female	African American (Black)	Industrial Engineering Intern	Aerospace Industry
P2	Industrial and Systems Engineering	Female	White	Materials and Production Intern	Power and Energy Industry
P3	Chemical Engineering	Female	White	Production Services Engineer	Manufacturing Industry
P4	Aerospace Engineering	Female	White	Engineering Co-Op	Defense Industry
P5	Computer Engineering	Male	White	Software Engineer	Aerospace Industry

Data were analyzed by three researchers using an open coding approach [16] there were several rounds of team discussions where the researchers discussed an initial codebook and in the second data analysis round inter-rater reliability tests were conducted to identify reliability of the coding process [16]. The process was conducted using the DEDOOSE qualitative software. In cases where there was disagreement about codes, discussions were held until agreement was reached.

3 RESULTS

From our analysis, several key patterns emerged across the participants' qualitative responses on their internship experiences. There was a total of 361 excerpts coded from the interview data, and the following themes were the most prevalent among the participants:

3.1 Boundary Spanning

Most of the participants agreed that they were involved as 'boundary spanners' who have linked or connected with others across three types of boundaries during their internship experience, including intra-team boundaries, inter-organizational boundaries, and hierarchical boundaries. Participants in the interview frequently discussed how boundary spanning across different teams helped them build and maintain communication networks and relationships among team members in the organization. One of the participants emphasized on the use of intra-team boundary spanning by building a strong relationship and trust which helped in getting resources including technical support and project funding. This particular boundary spanning theme is exemplified by the quote below:

If I needed something that I didn't have, my [team members] were quick to order it or if I needed something they were like, "Oh you can talk to this person and they can tell you more about it. If it's in the plant, they know everything that's in the plant so you can get it from them." Like I was never short of resources. They gave me as much money as I needed. I just had to explain to them why I needed it, what I was going to do with it, and if I needed enough for whatever span of time, I needed it for. So, I always had resources for my project and also resources to talk to as well. [P1]

There were other participants who went through multiple types of boundary spanning within the organization at the same time. They emphasized on working with different people during the internship experience, which involved their supervisors, and peer and shop floor employees, representing all three different types of boundaries. One of the participants highlighted the use of boundary spanning in multiple levels to solve problems in the workplace. The participant also discussed about understanding people's perspective in workplace at different levels and learning how to deal with them in order to solve problems. The quote below exemplifies the participant's boundary spanning experience:

I think that the place where I did most boundary spanning would be in the quality issue as solutions. I would travel with my manager to the manufacturing site and we would have to coordinate with the schedulers to make sure that our product was happening when you wanted it. And then also with the business team telling them we're doing this, or like if we have to do a trial afterwards to make sure that they knew what was going on, how it could affect the business. And then working with different people on the floor, getting their opinions on what we would come in and say, this is a problem that's happening. I think that you'd get a lot of different perspectives in different people when you do that kind of thing

and you have to make sure that you're considering everyone's opinion fairly and equally. [P3]

3.2 Knowledge/Learning

A prevalent theme across the participants' responses was knowledge and learning, referring to any instance of learning new things or demonstrating the use of previous knowledge in the workplace. Participants emphasized the importance of knowledge and learning in their internship, though the focus of this learning often varied. Perhaps most commonly mentioned was the need to learn specific tasks related to their job. This type of learning was typically grounded in a specific job responsibility, such as technical drawing, as one participant discussed:

I remember that the first day I went home and I, like, researched using a laser cutter and, like, the different lenses and all that good stuff. And then I was like, okay, I had to brush up on my CAD designs because I hadn't done that since freshman year. [P1]

Specific skills like these were typically technical in nature and directly related to the engineering tasks assigned to them. Others mentioned learning to use specific machines, understanding complex engineering processes, or familiarizing themselves with a new software. But participants also discussed the value of learning more broadly about their field or industry. For many, internships became the first time they experienced their major outside the classroom, giving them a first-hand look at the type of work performed in the field. A participant from chemical engineering reflected on her experience:

I think that since I was in a CBG company, I was a little less ... you're using separations in this big huge plant, and you're applying that knowledge, but it was a lot of seeing how the manufacturing and the R&D intermingled with each other and how the company worked through a work flow, stuff like that. [P3]

Using the internship as a chance to gain exposure to the field provided her with the chance to see how manufacturing and research worked hand in hand to produce a product. Leveraging the internship an opportunity to acquaint herself with the field provided her with real-world experience in her major.

For others, the internship was less about learning specific things, and more about learning itself. In fact, a few participants specifically recognized learning to learn as one of the biggest advantages of doing an internship. One student talked about it in terms of making mistakes:

I realize like this is your chance to make mistakes. This is your chance to learn. Like they want you to learn on your own. And so you don't have to come in knowing everything because you're supposed to learn it as you're there or else you're not really going to grow if you already know stuff and you're just going through the motions of it. So, it was really exciting not knowing something and then wanting to prove to them and to myself that I can do it. [P1]

For most participants, their internship was an opportunity to learn and grow their knowledge. This learning came in different forms. For some, it was a chance to learn a specific task relevant to their responsibilities. For others, it was an opportunity to better understand their major and their industry. But for many, it was less about learning specific things, and more about using the internship itself to make mistakes and learn outside the classroom.

3.3 Problems

Not surprisingly, participants discussed the problems they faced while interning. These problems tended to fall into one of two categories: technical and professional. Technical problems were typically encountered in relation to the project the participant was working on, as one participant explained:

... So, I came out with the idea of going to...of doing a lot of simulations as close to straight as possible to be able to predict that motion. And that I was able to do. But there is a lot of times where he would give me a lot of guidance but didn't know how to get there. So, it was a little...I learned a lot of problem-solving strategies while working there. [P4]

Here the participant describes running into a technical problem associated with predicting a behaviour, even describing the process she went through to address the challenge. These technical problems were the most common type of problem mentioned during the interviews, but professional (or non-technical) problems were often encountered in working with others during the internship. These problems were related to finding work, getting help, cooperating with others, and other issues. For example, one participant reflected on seeking help and mismatched expectations:

I think my biggest challenge was definitely getting help from the people above me and from the people around me. I know that they have a lot of important work to be doing, but if I get assigned a role, it's obviously important enough for me to get it done. So a lot of times I would have people reschedule on you a lot or if I got into a meeting they'd be like, "Oh, well, I don't really think that's important," or they would kind of try and change my entire scope of what I was doing when I had developed it with my manager. [P3]

The participant expressed frustration not only with finding help from their co-workers, but also receiving conflicting opinions from those that agreed to help. Generally speaking, problems like these encountered throughout the internship interfered with the participants' work and became challenging both technically and professionally. Nevertheless, they gave participants a chance to improve their problem-solving skills and better understand the types of challenges often encountered in a professional engineering setting.

3.4 Communication/Coordination

A Communication and coordination together formed another important theme that participants mentioned in their interview. Participants frequently emphasized the importance of effective communication in the workplace. Effective communication

included knowing how to interact with different groups of people, including supervisors, clients, and shop floor employees, both in and outside of workplace. Communication also included demonstrating both formal and informal presentations at different organizational levels. In particular, one of the participants discussed on getting compliments from clients and team members after demonstrating effective communication skills through a formal presentation. The accomplishment is exemplified in the quote below:

I basically presented my work to the [Client Name] and just the feedback I got afterwards... The first [client] came up, he's like, "Your IQ must be amazing, because you're only a junior at [College Name]." They were coming up and they were like, "You're so young and you're accomplishing all this stuff," and I'm like, "Oh my God." I didn't realize that what I was doing was so impactful for the [Community Name]. That's the proudest moment of my life. I got in my car afterwards and I just smiled, and I went like this on my wheel. I was like, "Yes, like you did it." So, that was definitely my biggest accomplishment [P4]

Participants also spoke of coordination, specifically coordinating their own schedules. Often faced with multiple responsibilities and looming deadlines, they discussed having to organize their time to accomplish the tasks given to them. One participant reflected on her process:

And after our little huddle I would go back to my desk and then I would schedule what I wanted to do for the day. If I wanted to keep going with my shadow board fixtures, I would say well from this time to this time I would do like lines one, two and three and talk to them and try to make their shadow boards. And then from this time to this time I would train the contractor on the kidding initiative that we were doing. And so I'd train her and then I would tell her that these, and I would also make up like a plan for her to guide her with who goals she would have to meet for each week. So like each task that I would give me would take a while, but I made sure to a lot like specific times for that. [P1]

For many, internships became the first time they were required to structure their day on their own. Whereas some were accustomed to their schedules being organized around classes and extracurriculars while in school, their new role in the workplace emphasized the importance of effective time management. Generally speaking, both communication and coordination became highly important skills for most of the participants in their day-to-day activities.

3.5 Preparation

A During the interview, participants talked about using previous knowledge, activity or experience that helped them prepare to transition as interns. Much of the preparation centered around technical and professional skills developed in college that were successfully transferred to the internship. Participants highlighted the first-year engineering program which taught them both technical skills like programming, and professional skills like teamwork. According to most of the participants, these

skills were both important and necessary when they transitioned as interns and helped them in solving engineering problems in workplace. The quotes below exemplify the preparation of the participants from college:

The course really helped your mind evolve to think in an engineering way and just like approach problems as an engineer. If I'm given a problem, I make sure that I understand the problem so that I'm not doing extra work that wasn't needed to begin with. I didn't know that I was actually learning a lot in foundations even though like you know they teach you like all of the different types of engineering you're learning. Like I was like okay I'm using [Software], but I never saw [Software] again personally for me in my other classes. So just knowing that, oh I actually do use this stuff was like, oh I'm learning, I'm actually learning [P1]

I think that with the whole First-Year Engineering Program, you get a lot of team activities that you can do. And then, within chemical engineering, it is super technical, but they do throw in those classes and it's so hard that you really have to work with people in order to accomplish all of it. So, I think that I really did have that background in order to work on this. [P3]

3.6 Value of Internships

As in reflecting on their experiences, all participants shared their perceptions of the value internships provide to engineering students. Much of the value centered around learning new skills, both technical and professional. Some participants found these skills helpful as they moved back into the classroom after their internship, providing context for the material and even bolstering their presentation and other professional skills. Several participants appreciated being able to see first-hand what can be done with the degree they are pursuing, using the internship as a gauge for whether they were interested in the type of work they experienced. Other participants mentioned the value of making connections during their work experience, indicating their plans to leverage those connections as they move into the job market. One participant summarized the value of an internship broadly:

I think experiential learning in itself is very, very valuable. I would never have known what I like and what I don't like. I feel like internships really enable you to understand a holistic perspective, whether that's within your field, you know you gain different skills, you gain those technical and social and personable skills. I think it also affects our professional competencies, like global perspectives, and communication, leadership and I think that's what really makes students stand out, if they have more experiential learning opportunities. That is like it just enhances your overall like college experience, in my opinion. I really, really value experiential learning and so I feel like internships and co-ops overall are very beneficial. [P2]

Useful for a variety of reasons, internships were discussed in a positive light amongst almost all participants, cementing their role as a valuable experience outside the engineering curriculum.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work used a qualitative approach to understand engineering students' experiences with internships. In terms of limitations, the study had difficulty in recruiting participants for the interview due to unavailability and time constraint of many participants. However, the researchers are actively recruiting participants with similar experiences to broaden the research scope for future studies in this context. The results of the analysis led to the identification of six important themes. Each theme highlights an important aspect of internship, speaking to the variety of benefits these experiences provide. Among these was knowledge and learning. Throughout their internships, participants gained a diverse set of new knowledge, using the experience as an opportunity to learn about engineering processes, as well as their potential role within the engineering field, these results align with previous work on internships we have conducted in other contexts [17]. Learning also included professional skills like teamwork and communication which were necessary to accomplish project goals, this is consistent with previous findings of our work in teamwork and professional skills [18]. However, this did not take place without problems, as most participants mentioned both technical and professional challenges that occurred throughout their internships. Despite these problems, most participants described internships as highly valuable, allowing them to gain new skills, make connections, and experience the engineering field firsthand. The value of academic preparation both in terms of technical skills and professional skills were also highlighted by the participants, this reinforces the expectations posed by the ABET criteria [10]. With positive feedback from students' internship experience, we believe that internships add value to the student's learning in engineering and academic leaders need to encourage students in participating in internships or even find better ways to integrate internship experiences within the academic curriculum. The successful transfer of these skills helped them solve engineering problems and collaborate with people at different levels in the workplace. Participants have acknowledged the term 'boundary spanning' and described scenarios involving different types of boundary spanning which aligns with the theory we used for the study [9]. Our paper gives a preliminary understanding of internship experiences of engineering students and our current findings demonstrate that more research is required to understand students' experiences during their time outside of school in the complex engineering world.

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